

Analysis of public policy transfer processes: A first approach to the case of Chile Crece Contigo and Uruguay Crece Contigo.

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Transnational Policy Process Research: Issues,
Concepts and Cases

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”Because there are public problems that, by their nature and complexity, simply cannot wait.”

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A brief look at the context

”Chile Crece Contigo” and ”Uruguay Crece Contigo”.

Motivation/ A brief look at the context

- "Chile Crece Contigo" is a subsystem within the Social Protection Network in Chile, which aims to accompany, protect and support comprehensively, all children and their families, through actions and services of universal character. It is part of the program offer of the Chilean Ministry of Social Development and Family (MDSF).
- It is a consequence of the "Chile Solidario" program (Government of Ricardo Lagos, 2000-2006), emphasizing early childhood through a basic process based on different studies and pre-investments carried out between 2005 and 2006. It would later become the hallmark of Michelle Bachelet's first government.
- On the other hand, "Uruguay Crece Contigo" is a public policy of national coverage in Uruguay, aimed at consolidating a comprehensive protection system for families and early childhood. Under the National Directorate of Social Development of the Ministry of Social Development (MIDES), it was born as a result of the experience of "Canelones Crece Contigo" and the Chilean experience.
- My master's thesis research in public policy analyzed the dynamics of the actors involved in the formation of "Chile Crece Contigo".

Introduction

- The phenomenon of mobilization of ideas has raised in the last decades, an important academic interest that in Latin America and the Caribbean has shown an important contribution of several authors in the areas of diffusion and transfers, situated from several theoretical perspectives.
- The construction and formation of policies is not only made up of actors, resources and an institutional framework, but there are also offices, buildings, restaurants, notebooks, elevators, temporal and spatial organization. It is here where the actor-network theory (ART) adds value to the idea of interactions between subjects in the generation of policies (Pozas, M, et al., 2023).
- The construction and formation of public policies, expressed through the different dynamics that occur in the processes of policy production, requires a thorough knowledge and understanding of the interactions that arise between the different actors in the policy formation process (Subirats et al., 2012).

Introduction

- In both cases of policy transfer and dissemination, the role of actors/agents is key. Its importance lies in their participation during the process that takes place, so that they intervene in one way or another, based on their capacities to mobilize resources vis-à-vis others to carry out certain specific courses of action and achieve their determined objectives (Dussauge 2012; Porto de Oliveira et al. 2020; Dente and Subirats 2014).
- On the other hand, social policy is a tool in which governments seek to influence poverty, income distributions and all those inequities that affect the population. It is essential to channel the energy of social conflict in order to mediate it and respond through goods and services that generate public value (Flores & Ruiz, 2022).
- A relevant framework of analysis corresponds to that of "epistemic communities", understood as those constituted by a limited group of participants, who believe in certain principles and causalities. Their membership is related to certain professions or disciplines whose knowledge is validated by providing legitimacy vis-à-vis others in society (Gómez, 2019; Osorio, 2017).

Methodology

In this initial exploratory phase of research, an inquiry work was conducted where unstructured personal interviews were considered (Marradi et al. 2018), which met the characteristics of those relevant actors of the process (proxy actors), representing 10% of the total number of interviews contemplated in the overall research.

Scope	General description
Design	Flexible design and of a mixed nature in its methodological scope. Placing the case study as its base design, allowing to deepen the analysis of the policy transfer process through the "process-tracing method".
Unit of analysis	Actors involved in the transfer process between both programs.
Sample	At this stage, 10% of the total sample was considered.
Instruments	Informal and unstructured guiding questions.
Processing and analysis	Using comparative analysis and network analysis techniques. Five categories of analysis were defined: nature of the policy, motives for the transfer, transfer channels, perceptions and experiences of actors and contextual variables.

Table 1. Methodological structure of exploratory stage of doctoral research. Source: Own elaboration

Methodology

About the analytical categories....

Categoría	Subcategorías	Descripción/característica
Naturaleza de la política	Tipo de política	¿Es una política innovadora, una reforma de una política existente, o una política adaptada?
	Área de política	¿Se trata de salud, educación, medio ambiente, etc.?
	Objetivos de la política	¿Cuáles son los objetivos que se buscan alcanzar con la transferencia?
Motivos para la transferencia	Factores internos	¿Existen motivaciones internas (ej: mejora de la calidad, respuesta a demandas) o externas (ej: presión de la sociedad civil, condiciones de financiamiento) que impulsan la transferencia?
	Percepciones sobre la política de "origen"	¿Se percibe la política fuente como exitosa, eficiente, o como un modelo a imitar?
	Motivaciones individuales	¿Cuáles son las motivaciones individuales de los actores involucrados en la transferencia?
Canales de transferencia	Procesos formales e informales	¿Se utilizan canales formales (ej: convenciones, acuerdos internacionales) o informales (ej: redes de expertos, blogs, etc.)?
	Participantes	¿Quiénes participan en la transferencia? ¿Expertos, políticos, funcionarios, sociedad civil?
	Dinámica de las relaciones	¿Cómo se construyen y se mantienen las relaciones entre los actores involucrados en la transferencia?
Percepciones y experiencias de los actores	Perspectivas individuales	¿Cuáles son las percepciones y experiencias de los actores involucrados en la transferencia (ej: funcionarios, políticos, expertos, sociedad civil)?
	Satisfacción con la política	¿Cómo se percibe la satisfacción con la política en el contexto receptor?
	Lecciones aprendidas	¿Qué lecciones se han aprendido del proceso de transferencia?
Variables contextuales	Contexto político	¿Cuál es el contexto político en el que se produce la transferencia?
	Contexto social	¿Cuál es el contexto social en el que se produce la transferencia?
	Contexto económico	¿Cuál es el contexto económico en el que se produce la transferencia?

Table 2. Categories of analysis. Source: Own elaboration

Methodology

On categories and their analysis of decisional networks....

Where:

$$e_{i,j} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{no existe relación completa entre actores} \\ 1, & \text{existe relación completa entre actores} \end{cases}$$

$e_i = \text{actor o agente en proceso}$

Categorías	Matrices de adyacencia
Naturaleza de la política	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
Motivos para la transferencia	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
Canales de transferencia	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
Percepciones y experiencias de actores	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$
VARIABLES contextuales	$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$

Table 3. Adjacency matrices associated with the categories. Source: Own elaboration

Results

In relation to the findings found in this first stage of initial exploration, these results will be presented in their two aspects of analysis, in order to maintain both consistency and coherence with what was indicated at the methodological procedural level.

Results

1.- Comparative analysis

Categories	General findings
Nature of the policy	There is a convergence where it is perceived that policy transfer with other countries is actually the consequence of an ongoing process of cooperation and exchange between different working groups (academic, technical and political) in the period both before and after the one analyzed.
Reasons for the transfer	Shared vision on the work and experience achieved in the public health sector, more specifically in what refers to the infant-maternal area, central axis of the ChCC program. Together with a highly successful, efficient and sustainable program perspective based on scientific and technical evidence.
Transfer channels	Strong relationships through informal and formal channels, seen as conversations between peers from the same academic and technical (epistemic) community, as well as through forums, technical assistance or exchange teams belonging to early childhood networks. The relationship dynamics were based on early contact in the areas of public health, developmental psychology, economics, pediatrics, as well as teams from universities, international organizations and civil society.

Table 4. Results of comparative analysis by category. Source: Own elaboration

Results

1.- Comparative analysis

Categories	General findings
Perceptions and experiences of stakeholders	<p>This process had a strong driving force on the part of a network or specific groups in different areas related to early childhood, which channeled efforts to involve specific sectors of countries, which later led to more concrete processes being supported by different international organizations.</p> <p>Existence of a perception of ChCC as a satisfactory and pioneering policy in the area, strongly linked to the territorial needs of the target groups, which was essential for the interest shown by other countries.</p>
Contextual variables	<p>The stakeholders consider that during the period there was an ideological affinity between different governments in the region, as well as a convergence between communities and academic groups.</p> <p>The existence of common elements in terms of poverty and inequality of the target groups made it appropriate to move forward with interventions with characteristics closer to others coming from the developed world.</p>

Table 5. Results of comparative analysis by category. Source: Own elaboration

Results

2.- Decisional network analysis

Considering the comparative analyses carried out according to the categories indicated, a network analysis graph was constructed for each one, in order to show the relationships between actors according to the answers given in the interview process. Each category presents an incidence matrix, which, in turn, is later interpreted visually as a graph.

Results

2.- Analysis of decisional networks

Nature of the policy

Figure 1. Graph visualization corresponding to the analysis category "nature of policy".
Source: Own elaboration

Results

2.- Analysis of decisional networks

Motives for transfer

Figure 2. Graph visualization corresponding to the analysis category "motives for transfer". Source: Own elaboration

Results

2.- Analysis of decisional networks

Transfer channels

Figure 3. Graph visualization corresponding to the analysis category "transfer channels".
Source: Own elaboration

Results

2.- Analysis of decisional networks

Stakeholder perceptions and experiences

Figure 4. Graph visualization corresponding to the analysis category "perceptions and experiences of stakeholders". Source: Own elaboration

Results

2.- Analysis of decisional networks

Contextual variables

Figure 5. Graph visualization corresponding to the analysis category "contextual variables". Source: Own elaboration

Discussion

- The preliminary use of "proxy" actors that present characteristics equivalent to those of the agents involved in the study process, provides relevant information for an early interpretation of the phenomenon of policy diffusion and transfer.
- There are limitations to this first approximation, particularly in using only a fraction of all the instruments for data collection, as well as for complete processing and analysis. For this reason, it is considered with both its own strengths and weaknesses.
- There are relevant elements that come to show a possible process analysis scenario that I would consider as key points:
 - ❖ The already existing cooperation between different working groups.
 - ❖ Sustainability
 - ❖ Success and efficiency of the ChCC program in the light of other countries.
 - ❖ Strong component of experts and technicians in the area of early childhood.
 - ❖ Key would be the epistemic community as a promoter agent and a similar political, social, economic and ideological context among countries in the region.

Thank you!

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